

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates: 25 September – 7 October 2022

Report published: May 2023

**From elephants to cats to ants:
Monitoring biodiversity of Vwaza
Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi**

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Authors:

Benjamin Hintz
Lilongwe Wildlife Trust

Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

ABSTRACT

Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists supported Lilongwe Wildlife Trust (LWT) research projects for a third time in 2022, between 25 September and 7 October, conducting the following research activities:

Elephant herd sightings and dung sampling: In recent years, human-elephant conflict has become an increasing threat to people's livelihoods, but also for the local elephant population. A new fence was constructed in 2021 along the southern and eastern boundaries of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve (VMWR), aiming to keep elephants within the reserve and reduce conflict. Elephant herd sightings were conducted around Lake Kazuni and resulted in 42 observations of family herds or single bulls. 49% of all elephants observed were in the age categories younger than 16, suggesting a stable population recruitment. For future expeditions, identification of matriarchs would be beneficial to monitor herd compositions and natality and mortality rates within herds. Dung samples were collected ad lib to assess if there were any cultivated food items contained in them, which would indicate that elephants still managed to venture into community land. No cultivated food items were found in 38 collected dung samples.

Hippo transects: VMWR is the only protected area in Malawi's northern region to host a stable hippo population. However, no consistent monitoring of their populations is being done. As Lake Kazuni and the adjacent South Rukuru River are the only perennial water sources in the reserve, the majority of the population should be concentrated there. Transects of the northern shore of the lake were completed six times and resulted in a total of 698 hippos counted, with a maximum of 120 during two of the transects, which serves as a conservative population estimate. Compared to previous years, the maximum count has decreased substantially (from 338 in 2018 and 169 in 2019), suggesting a population decline. Future expeditions should keep monitoring the hippo population to recognise population crashes.

Camera trapping: Camera trapping is used worldwide as a non-intrusive remote monitoring method, particularly for elusive and cryptic species that are difficult to monitor through older, more conventional methods. 14 camera traps were deployed along roads in the southern area of the reserve, and an additional 3 at baited sites. 447 pictures with animals from 26 different species were recorded. Compared to previous expeditions, 3 new species were recorded: African wild dog, Selous's mongoose and Sharpe's grysbok. Four individual wild dogs were identified, which likely formed a dispersal group. African wild dogs had not been seen in VMWR in 20 years, substantiating the value of camera traps for monitoring.

Invertebrate sampling: VMWR is being considered as a release site for pangolins rehabilitated by the LWT. Pangolins depend on ants as a food source. However, no data on ant composition inside the reserve was available. A grid of baited pitfall invertebrate traps was set up in two representative habitat types: woodland and floodplains. Seven different ant species were identified during the sampling. Capture rates of these species did not significantly differ between habitats. During a previous research project, the LWT aimed to identify preferred ant species for pangolins, three of which were also identified in VMWR. Among other invertebrates captured, nine different taxonomic orders were represented.

Hyaena call-ins: Spotted hyaenas are the most abundant and widespread large carnivore in Africa. However, their conservation status is often overlooked. Despite this, they can influence other species' populations and can serve as indicators of ecosystem health. Call-ins via audio playback to attract animals are a commonly used method to estimate hyaena populations. Three call-in events were conducted at baited sites and camera traps deployed to monitor hyaena activity after departure. No hyaenas were observed during the call-ins, nor were vocalisations in response to the call-ins recorded. The next expedition will try again, with an adapted methodology.

iNaturalist: iNaturalist is an online platform and application compiling evidence-based observations of organisms globally, making the data publicly accessible to researchers. Participants of the expedition uploaded 397 observations of 138 different species. A large proportion of observations was added from pictures taken during the invertebrate sampling project.

CHIYAMBI

Gulu la akatswiri la Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists linapeleka thandizo kokwana katatu mchaka cha 2022 ku bungwe la Lilongwe Wildlife Trust (LWT) pantchito zokhudzana ndi kafukufuku mmiyezi ya September 25 komanso October pa 7:

Njobvu (kupezeka kwa gulu la njobvu komanso kuunika ndowe zake): Mu zaka zapitazi udani pakati pa anthu ndi Njobvu wadzetsa chiwopsezo pa moyo wa anthu ndi chiwerengelo cha Njobvu. Mpanda watsopano unamangidwa mchaka cha 2021 kuzungulira dera la Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve (VMWR), (kummwera komanso kummawa) ndi cholinga chakuti Njobvu zitetezeke komanso kuchepetsa chiwopsezo. Poyendera malowa mdera la Nyanja ya Kazuni zotsatila zake zinawonetsa kuti Njobvu zinapezeka zokwana 42 kuphatikiza zazimuna komanso zazikazi ndi ana. Pa Njobvu 100, zokwana 49 zinali zochepelela zaka 16 zomwe zinawonetsa kuti chiwerengelo cha Njobvu chili bwino. Kutengela ndi ma ulendo ena amtsogolo, zidzakhala zothandiza kudziwa Njobvu zazikazi, kabelekedwe komanso kutalika kwa moyo wa Njobvu. Ndowe za Njobvu zinawunikidwa kuti tipeze ngati Njobvu zimadya mbewu zomwe ziwonetse kuti Njobvu zimalowelera mminda ya wanthu mmudzi. Koma mu ndowe za Njobvu 38 munalibe chisonyezo cha zakudya zina zilizonse.

Mvuwu: VMWR ndi malo otetezedwa muno mu Malawi mdera la kumpoto omwe ali abata osungila Mvuwu. Koma, tsoka lake palibe kuyang'anila kulikonse kwa chiwerengelo cha Mvuwu komwe kukuchitika. Malo omwe Mvuwu zingapeze madzi akumwa ndi a mnyanja ya Kazuni komanso mtsinje wa South Rukuru, ndi malo omwe Mvuwu zikuyenera kutsatilako. Malire anakhazikitsidwa kumpoto kwa nyanjayi ndipo anatenga ma ulendo asanu ndi kamodzi kuti amalizidwe choncho zotsatila zake Mvuwu zokwana 698 zinaikidwa nkawundula omwe unatenga Mvuwu 120 mmagawo awiri amalilewa. Izi ndi zomwe zikuwonetsa chiwerengero cha Mvuwu zotetezedwa. Kusiyanyitsa ndi zaka zammbuyomu, chiwerengelo chatsika (kuchokera pa 338 mchaka cha 2018 kufika 169 mchaka cha 2019). Zomwe zikutanthauza kuti chiwerengero chatsika. Ma ulendo ena amtsogolo akuyenera ayang'anile chiwerengelo cha Mvuwu kuti adziwe kukula kwa chiwerengero.

Kujambula ndi Kamera: Kugwiritsa ntchito Kamera ndi njira yomwe padziko lonse lapansi kunawanda chifukwa sikusokoneza chilengedwe ngati njira yoyang'anila zinyama maka kwa mitundu ya zinyama zomwe zimavuta kuyang'anila pogwiritsa ntchito njira zamake dzana. Zipangizo za Kamera zokwana 14 zinaikidwa mmbali mwa nsewu kumvuma kwa dera lotetezedwali komanso ena atatu mmalo okhazikika. Zithunzi zokwanila 447 za zinyama zosiyansiyana zokwana 26 zinajambulidwa: Nkhandwe, mimbulu ndi aGwape. Nkhandwe zokwanila zinayi zinawoneka zomwe mwachidziwikile zinali pazokha. Nkhandwe zakhala osawoneka mzaka 20 zapitazi zomwe zikutsindika kufunika kojambula ndi Kamera.

Nyama zokwawa: Pali ganizo lakuti malo a VMWR akhale osungilako ndi kuchiza zinyama za Pangolini (Ngaka) ndi a bungwe la LWT. Ma Pangolin amadya tizilombo kapena inswa zomwe ndi zakudya zawo. Komabe palibe kalemba wina aliyense wa inswa ndi tizilombo mmalo otetezedwawa. Mmalo angapo munaikidwa matchera. Malo amenewa ndi pamtunda komanso mnkhalango. Inswa ndi tizilombo tokwanila mitundu 7 zinapezeka koma zambiri zinali zofanana. Mu kafukufuku wina wammbuyomu bungwe la LWT linali ndi cholinga chofuna kudziwa inswa zimene zimakondedwa ndi ma Pangolin, zitatu za inswa zinapezeka ndi a VMWR. Nyama zina zokwawa zinajambulidwa ndipo panapezeka kusiyana kwina ndi kwina.

Afisi (Kuitaniza afisi): Afisi omwe anawoneka anali ambiri ndipo ali ponseponse mu Africa omwe ali mu gulu lakudya zimnyama zinzake. Koma chitetezo cha afisi sichimawerengeledwa nthawi zambiri. Ngakhale zili chonchi chiwerengelo chake chimathandizila umoyo ndi chiwerengero cha zinyama zina. Muitano kudzera mnjira yosewelera nyimbo yomwe ndi njiranso ina imathandiza kudziwa chiwerengelo cha afisi. Mchitidwe wa chiwerengelochi wotelewu wapangikako katatu mmalo angapo oikika omwe anali ndi zipangizo za Kamera. Panalibe fisi ndi mmodzi yemwe pamene muitano unalizidwa. Komanso panalibenso mang'ombe ena ali wonse omwe anajambulidwa. Ulendo wina tidzayesetsa kugwiritsa njira ina.

iNaturalist: iNaturalist ndi njira yogwiritsa ntchito intaneti posungila mbiri ndi uthenga komanso umboni weniweni wa tizilombo pa Dziko lonse yomwe imathandiza kuti anthu opanga kafukufuku apezere uthenga. Gulu lomwe limatenga nawo mbali pa ulendo uwu linasindikiza zotsatila zokwana 397 za zinyama mitundu 138. Pa zochitika izi panaphatikizidwa zithunzi zazinyama zina zokwawa zambiri ndithu.

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1. Expedition Review

Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

Background information, location conditions and the research area are as per [Harwood et al. \(2019\)](#). The citizen science expedition in Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve (VMWR) in northern Malawi focused on biodiversity surveying. All data contributed to a long-term dataset and monitoring programme in VMWR and the larger Malawi-Zambia Transfrontier Conservation Area, and are shared with local managing groups to empower and influence effective conservation strategies.

1.2. Dates & team

The project ran for one 13-day group from 25 September to 7 October 2022, composed of a team of national and international citizen scientists, professional scientists and an expedition leader. Dates were chosen to coincide with the dry season in Malawi and its corresponding ease of access to the reserve and wildlife sightings.

The expedition team was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

Chris Baranowski (UK), Janet Bellairs (UK), Isabelle Fragniere (Switzerland), Evelyn Frey-Royston (Germany), Robyn Gray (USA), Daniela Gunz (Switzerland), Lynn Harr (USA), Matthias Herold (Germany), Imelda Richardson (UK), Arthur Roose (Netherlands), Gitta Voss (Netherlands), Elizabeth Williams (USA).

On site field scientists were:

Olivia Sievert – Head of Biodiversity Research, Lilongwe Wildlife Trust
Pilirani Sankhani – Senior Field Research Coordinator, Lilongwe Wildlife Trust
Benjamin Hintz – Field Research Coordinator, Lilongwe Wildlife Trust

The expedition leader Roland Arnison studied Environmental Science and is a qualified Mountain Leader, a Mountain Rescue volunteer and has led a variety of expeditions in the UK, Canada, Iceland and Namibia, including introducing young people to the joys and challenges of expeditions in wild places. He has run expedition citizen science projects ranging from sampling for plastic pollution in the ocean to searching for the elusive Collared Pika in the Yukon as a bio-indicator of climate change. Roland's mountaineering exploits have taken him to un-climbed peaks in the Himalayas and equally challenging times in the Scottish hills in winter. Roland enjoys kayaking, climbing, cycling, filming, photography, diving and sometimes just walking in some wonderful and wild parts of the world. He has also spent many years looking after a smallholding in Yorkshire, creating wildlife habitats, and experimenting with novel food growing and renewable energy projects.

A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place, but did not have to be invoked because there were no medical or other incidents.

1.3. Partner

The Lilongwe Wildlife Trust (LWT) was established in 2009 and has grown into one of Malawi's leading conservation NGOs. LWT's mission is to save wildlife, campaign for conservation justice and inspire people to value and protect nature in Malawi. Working in collaboration with local and international partners, the trust responds to urgent conservation challenges and drives long-term social and institutional change. It runs several projects across five programme areas: wildlife rescue and rehabilitation, wildlife research, environmental education, community conservation and wildlife advocacy and enforcement. LWT has 90 staff working across three offices and several field sites across the country. The government of Malawi has appointed LWT to administer a number of national wildlife management, justice, and advocacy initiatives. They are also a member of the International Union for Conservation of Nature, the Malawi representative for the Species Survival Network, and the Secretariat for the Malawi Parliamentary Conservation Caucus.

1.4. Acknowledgements

We are very grateful to all the expedition citizen scientists, who not only dedicated their spare time to helping but also, through their expedition contributions, funded the research. We would also like to thank our key partners, the DNPW for supporting our programme and assisting with local expertise, logistics and of course assistance from the wildlife rangers. We would like to thank Elephants for Africa (EfA) for developing the elephant research protocols. Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank members of the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions and donors for their sponsorship, as well as Olivia Sievert, Benjamin Hintz, Pilirani Sankhani, Tom Mixer and Jonny Vaughan for their hard work in making the expedition a reality. We extend our appreciation to our expedition cooks Brenda Thera and Finesse Phiri.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org. Enquires should be addressed to Biosphere Expeditions at the address given on the website. Also available are:

All expedition reports, including this and previous expedition reports:

<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Expedition diary/blog:

<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/malawi-2022/>

Pictures, videos, media coverage of the expedition:

<https://www.biosphere-expeditions.org/malawi>

1.6. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist paid a contribution of €2,900 per person per twelve-day period towards expedition costs. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special research equipment and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	35.895
Expenditure	
Base camp includes board & lodging and all services	11,489
Transport includes hire cars, fuel, taxis and other in-country transport	2,601
Equipment & hardware includes research materials & gear etc. purchased internationally & locally	2,938
Staff includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff salaries and travel expenses	10,613
Administration includes miscellaneous fees & sundries	138
Team recruitment Malawi As estimated % of annual PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	3,998
Income – Expenditure	4,118
Total percentage spent directly on project	89%

2. Elephant herd sightings

Benjamin Hintz
Lilongwe Wildlife Trust

2.1. Introduction

Best estimates of elephant (*Loxodonta africana*) populations in Malawi suggest a 71% decline in elephants between 2002 and 2006 alone (Thouless et al, 2016). Since the 1970s, elephants across Malawi, including Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve (VMWR), have been heavily poached for their ivory and subjected to human-wildlife conflict persecution. Threats to elephant populations in Malawi differ from most other range states, because Malawi is a small country with a very high population density and therefore human population pressure, few contiguous protected areas (only 9% of the country is protected) (Blanc et al. 2007) and the second highest rate of deforestation in Southern Africa (UNEP 2002). Elephant populations in Malawi are small and isolated, only remaining in protected areas, which are decreasing due to human encroachment and deforestation (Blanc et al. 2007). Malawi's elephants are geographically important as they provide a transboundary link to priority populations (as listed by the African Elephant Conservation Fund) in the Luangwa-Zambezi Valley through the Malawi-Zambia Transfrontier Conservation Area (MZTFCA, 30,621 km²), which includes VMWR, along with Nyika and Kasungu National Parks in Malawi. The MZTFCA facilitates elephant dispersal, movements, and genetic diversity. Elephants in Malawi are suffering from increasing isolation caused by decreasing connectivity through agricultural expansion and human encroachment (Thouless et al. 2016).

Regardless of these large transboundary conservation areas, isolation, encroachment and habitat loss are threatening elephant populations in Malawi (Munthali 1998). Yet management and conservation initiatives are limited by a lack of rigorous research and survey data (Blanc et al. 2007, Table 2.1a). Over 50% of elephant population estimates are low-quality guesses (Blanc et al. 2007) and surveys are not standardised nor rigorous, thus limiting interpretation of elephant status and trends across Malawi.

There has been no previous systematic census or monitoring of the elephant populations in VMWR. In 2015 a total of 203 elephants were counted on the VMWR aerial survey (Macpherson 2015). However, the exact number of elephants that make use of VMWR year around is unknown, as it is thought that some of the population migrate within the larger MZTFCA throughout the year (NEAPM 2015, Sievert et al. 2021).

Table 2.1a. Elephant population estimates in Malawi (IUCN, 2016)

Input Zone	Cause of Change ¹		Survey Details ²			Number of Elephants		PFS ³	Area (km ²)	Map Location	
	Change	Type	Reliab.	Year	Estimate	95% C.L.	Source			Lon.	Lat.
+ Kasungu National Park	DT	AT	A	2014	40		Macpherson, 2015a	1	2,316	33.1E	12.9S
+ Liwonde National Park	DT	AT	A	2014	777		Macpherson, 2015b	1	675	35.3E	14.9S
+ Majete Wildlife Reserve	NG	O	D	2015	300		Fearnhead, pers. comm., 2015	1	860	34.6E	15.9S
+ Nkhosakota Wildlife Reserve	DT	GS	D	2013	92		Sichali & Mkumbwa, 2014	1	747	34.1E	13.0S
+ Nyika National Park	DT	AT	A	2013	47		Macpherson, 2013b	1	1,679	33.8E	10.6S
+ Phiri Longwe Forest Reserve	NG	O	D	2009	6		Kaunga-Nyirenda, pers. comm., 2014	1	640	35.0E	14.5S
+ Thumba and Detsza Salima Forest Reserves	DT	GT	A	2015	133		Clifford, 2016	1	418	34.3E	14.0S
+ Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve	DT	AT	A	2013	310		Macpherson, pers. comm., 2013c	1	978	33.4E	11.0S

* Range of informed guess

¹Key to Causes of Change (only tracked since 2007): DA: Different Area; DD: Data Degraded; DT: Different Technique; NA: New Analysis; NG: New Guess; NP: New population; PL: Population Lost; PS: Repeat Survey (PS denotes a repeat survey that is not statistically comparable for reasons such as different season); —: No Change

²Key to Survey Types: AC: Aerial Count, not specified; AS: Aerial Sample Count; AT: Aerial Total Count; DC: Dung Count; EX: Extrapolation from GIS; GD: Genetic Dung Count; GS: Ground Sample Count; GT: Ground Total Count; IG: Informed Guess; IR: Individual Registration; OG: Other Guess; Survey Type is followed by an indicator of survey quality, ranked from 1 to 3 (best to worst). Survey Reliability is keyed A-E (best to worst) as outlined in this table.

³PFS: Priority for Future Surveys, ranked from 1 to 5 (highest to lowest). Based on the precision of estimates and the proportion of national range accounted for by the site in question, PFS is a measure of the importance and urgency for future population surveys. All areas of unassessed range have a priority of 1. See Introduction for details on how the PFS is derived.

2.2. Methods

In the height of the dry season, one of the sole perennial water sources within VMWR is Lake Kazuni and the associated South Rukuru River. These areas are utilised heavily in the dry season by elephants for drinking, swimming, bathing and to cover themselves in mud and sand. We therefore undertook herd counts around Lake Kazuni. It was expected that this would also help prevent potential double counts of herds when travelling to and from the water source. Furthermore, VMWR has been identified as an area of risk for Human African Trypanosomiasis (Lemerani et al., 2020), however, Lake Kazuni is devoid of tsetse flies, the primary host of Human African Trypanosomiasis. The risk of contraction was deemed significant enough to restrict expedition surveying efforts to the central region of the reserve.

Herd counts were conducted once daily, either from a vehicle or foot and opportunistically from base camp. Counts from base camp were only conducted when no citizen scientists were out to collect data on elephant herds, or when the group had already passed the location where the herd approached from and thus the herd was missed on that count. To prevent double counting during the latter occasion, confirmation if the herd had already been counted was established via radio communication. During counts, herd compositions were established by assessing the sexes and ages of individuals, broadly classifying them into infants (1-2), juveniles (3-10), sub-adults (11-15) and adults (16+). Along with herd compositions, time and GPS coordinates of the encounter, the habitat type the herd was first observed in, and the distance and bearing to the herd were also recorded. Each group encountered was assigned a confidence level (1-3), representing the likelihood of observing all individuals in the herd (1 = 100%), roughly half (2 = 50%) or being uncertain about the total group size (3).

2.3. Results

Throughout the expedition, nine herd counts were conducted resulting in a total of 28 herd observations and 14 observations of single bulls. Of these, 22 observations were conducted from base camp (Figure 2.3a), 18 and 2 were conducted by vehicle and on-foot, respectively.

Average elephants encountered per day was 50.89 ± 33.05 SD (range: 13-122), excluding observations of single bulls, average herd size encountered was 15.86 ± 18.42 SD (range: 4-105; Figure 2.3b).

A total of 457 individual elephant observations occurred over the expedition period. Of all observed individuals, 51% were adults, 19.5% subadults and 29.5% were infants or juveniles (Figure 2.3c).

Figure 2.3a. Location of elephant observations conducted during the 2022 expedition. Higher intensity of heat clusters indicates larger group size.

Figure 2.3b. Total elephant counts per sample day with demographic composition indicated.

Figure 2.3c. Proportion of age classes observed during the expedition elephant counts. Infants/juveniles (≤ 10 years), subadults (11-15 years) and adults (≥ 16 years).

2.4. Discussion

Elephants have a long gestation period of 22 months and calving intervals of 3-7 years (Hanks and McIntosh 1973). Puberty in males is only reached between 12 and 22 years, whereas females start breeding at the age of 7 and most conceive their first calf by 11 (Buss and Smith 1966). Reproduction is therefore extremely slow and negative impacts on natality or mortality rates can affect population recruitment drastically. No consistent data on natality and mortality rates are available for VMWR, as such population trends need to be evaluated through direct population monitoring. Nearly half of all observed elephants were in the age group younger than 16, which indicates good reproductive success within the population.

Previous population counts for VMWR estimated a population of 310 individuals in 2013 and then 203 individuals in 2015 (Macpherson 2015). Because individuals were not being identified, double counts of individuals travelling back to Lake Kazuni for a second time in one day was possible. However, herd size and composition were established, from which it was determined that double counting on a single day did not occur. The highest single day count was 122 individuals, which represented over half of the 2015 population. As the 2022 expedition took place during the end of the dry season, elephants were dependent on getting water every 1-2 days and typically forage within 16 km of the nearest water source (Kerley et al. 2008). Therefore it is likely that a large proportion of the Vwaza elephant population was encountered around the lake and South Rukuru River during the expedition. Lake Kazuni therefore should be a focus for law enforcement patrols as an 'intensive protection zone' for the VMWR elephants during dry season (May-November).

2.5. Outlook for future expedition work

Continuous monitoring of elephant herd compositions provides reliable information on recruitment success and breeding output in the population. Furthermore, it has been shown as useful in identifying important 'hot-spot' areas, which can be identified as 'intense protection zones'. To further enhance the value of the collected data, identification of individual herds would allow long-term monitoring on a smaller scale and provide insights on herd-level natality and mortality rates. By creating identification profiles of the matriarchs of observed family herds, herds can be identified during future encounters and their composition compared to previous years.

2.6 Literature cited

- Blanc, J.J., Barnes, R.F.W., Craig, G.C., Dublin, H.T., Thouless, C.R., Douglas-Hamilton, I., and Hart, J.A. (2007) African elephant status report 2007: An update from the African Elephant Database. Occasional paper of the IUCN Species Survival Commission No. 33. IUCN/SSC African Elephant Specialist Group. IUCN, Gland, Switzerland. vi-276
- Buss, I. O. and Smith, N. S. (1966) Observations on Reproduction and Breeding Behavior of the African Elephant. *The Journal of Wildlife Management*. Vol 30(2), pp. 375-388
- Hanks, J., and McIntosh, J. E. A. (1973) Population dynamics of the African elephant (*Loxodonta africana*). *Journal of Zoology*. Vol. 169(1), pp. 29–38
- International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN) (2016) Malawi - 2016 African Elephant Status Report. https://africanelephantdatabase.org/report/2016/Africa/Southern_Africa/Malawi. Accessed on 03 January 2023
- Kerley, G. I. H., Landman, M., Kruger, L., Owen-Smith, N., Balvour, D., de Boer, W. F., Gaylard, A. Lindsay, K. and Slotow, R. (2008) Effects of Elephants on Ecosystems and Biodiversity. In: Mennell, K. G. and Scholes, R. J. (ed). *The 2007 scientific Assessment of Elephant Management in South Africa*. Pretoria: CSIR, pp. 101-147
- Lemerani, M., Jumah, F., Bessell, P., Biéler, S., and Mathu Ndung'u, J. (2020) Improved Access to Diagnostics for Rhodesian Sleeping Sickness around a Conservation Area in Malawi Results in Earlier Detection of Cases and Reduced Mortality. *Journal of Epidemiology and Global Health*. Vol. 10(4), pp. 280-287
- Munthali S.M. (1998). *The State of Biodiversity in Malawi*. Unpublished Consultancy Report. Ministry of Forestry, Fisheries and Environment.
- NEAPM. (2015) National elephant action plan for Malawi (pp. 1-55). Prepared for Malawi Department of National Parks and Wildlife
- Macpherson, D. (2015) Report on an aerial wildlife census of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi – October 2015. Unpublished, Department of National Parks and Wildlife. Malawi.
- Sievert, O., Evans, K., Mgoola, W. & Harwood, A. (2021) Early insights into the movement of Malawi's transboundary elephants. *African Journal of Ecology*. 1-5
- Thouless, C.R., Dublin, H.T., Blanc, J.J., Skinner, D.P., Daniel, T.E., Taylor, R.D., Maisels, F., Frederick, H.L., and Bouche, P. (2016) African elephant status report 2016: An update from the African Elephant Database. Occasional Paper Series of the IUCN Species Survival Commission. IUCN / SSC Africa Elephant Specialist Group IUCN 60; vi-309
- United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) (2002) Africa environment outlook: past, present and future perspectives. Available at: <http://www.grida.no/publications/80>. Accessed on 03 January 2023

3. Elephant dung sampling

Benjamin Hintz
Lilongwe Wildlife Trust

3.1. Introduction

Community land bordering VMWR has experienced high levels of human-elephant conflict in the past years (Sievert et al. 2022). Conflict increases towards the end of the dry season when the elephants frequently venture out of VMWR to feed on cultivated crops, as they provide a higher density of nutrients than foraging in natural habitat (Chiyo et al. 2005, Figure 3.1a). Although a few fencing initiatives have occurred along the southern boundary of VMWR over the years, this area was unfenced from 2018 until November 2021, allowing elephants easy access to cultivated land bordering the park. Over the years, elephant presence in agricultural land was confirmed through farmers' reports, tracks, dung and damaged crop items (Anthony & Wasambo 2009, Sievert et al., unpubl.).

Figure 3.1a. Cultivated crop presence in collected elephant dung samples in VMWR in 2018 and 2021 (Sievert et al., unpubl.).

Elephants are hindgut fermenters, retaining food only for a short time with minimal digestion (Greene et al. 2019). As large-bodied bulk feeders, only large food items require breaking down with their molars and smaller food items are often swallowed whole. As such, food items are passed through the gastro-intestinal tract and subsequently defecated relatively intact. Therefore seeds and sometimes whole fruits are visible in deposited dung piles and can be used to study the composition of elephant diet. As other indirect evidence of elephants can sometimes be easily missed (e.g. tracks on hard substrate), analysis of the contents of their diet is an additional method to evaluate potential human-elephant conflict levels by analysing the proportion of cultivated food items relative to naturally occurring ones. Searching for the presence of cultivated food items in elephant dung helps provide insight on the efficacy of the newly constructed VMWR fence alongside other mitigation measures along the reserve boundaries, such as targeted fence patrols and use of beehives as a deterrent.

3.2. Methods

Fresh dung samples (<12 hrs with no signs of decomposition or insect activity) were collected during any field activity and opportunistically around base camp when elephants had traversed the area. Dung was handled wearing protective gloves. For each dung pile, three intact boli were selected, and average diameter was measured along the long and short axes of the elliptical ends to estimate age of the elephant. The total number of boli in the dung pile and GPS location of collection were also recorded. The selected boli were stored in a labelled plastic bag until analysis.

For seed analysis, each sample was broken up on a plastic tray wearing protective gloves and any seeds contained within the sample were separated and cleaned in Dettol solution. Once completely dried, seeds were categorised and counted. Out of simplicity, seeds were categorised as “cultivated food items” and “natural food items” to allow for further analysis on diet within the protected area.

3.3. Results

38 dung samples were collected and analysed for the presence of cultivated food items. None of the samples collected contained cultivated crops or items that do not naturally occur in VMWR. The majority of samples were collected along the northern shore of Lake Kazuni (n = 27), where high levels of human-elephant conflict previously occurred (Figure 3.3a).

Figure 3.3.a. Location of elephant dung samples collected in VMWR during the expedition.

3.4. Discussion

All dung samples during the expedition period were collected around Lake Kazuni. Towards the end of the dry season, the lake and the South Rukuru river originating from it are the only permanent water sources within VMWR. Elephants are water-dependent, needing to drink every 1-2 days and they typically forage within 16 km of the nearest water source (Kerley et al., 2008). This implies that the lake should experience a higher occupation of elephants than other parts of the reserve during the dry season. This was observed on the elephant herd counts, which at times demonstrated that over half of the estimated population of elephants in VMWR visited Lake Kazuni during the day. Therefore, collecting dung samples around Lake Kazuni, although geographically restricted, should provide a representative sample of the population. Dung collection during 2018 and 2021 focused efforts on the same area (Sievert et al., unpubl.), which allows for comparison of results over the applicable years.

As VMWR was not fully fenced at the time of the expedition (only the southern and parts of the eastern boundary), there was a possibility of displaced conflict (i.e. elevated conflict in areas that were not yet fenced). However, all seeds found within the dung samples were from plants naturally occurring in VMWR and there was no evidence that elephants fed on cultivated foods during the expedition. As food retention is approximately 12 hours, the time before the expedition could not be evaluated. However, no elephant conflict was reported to the LWT in the months leading up to the expedition, which suggests the fence is working successfully in preventing human-elephant conflict. It is however important to note that while seeds and whole food items would be readily discernible in deposited dung, other commonly cultivated food items such as bananas, sweet potatoes, cassava and the leaves of crops such as pumpkin would not be easily observable and could be missed entirely. Elephant break-outs predominantly occur at night to avoid human detection (Graham et al. 2009). While assessment of dung has some clear biases and thus does not cover all potential food items consumed, it provides a reliable method to survey elephant diet without having to observe the animals directly.

3.5. Outlook for future expedition work

The newly constructed fence has successfully reduced human-elephant conflict along the southern boundary of VMWR to zero. However, it is possible for elephants to break through the fence or utilise areas into which the fence does not extend to venture into agricultural land. Furthermore, an extension of surveying to the end posts of the fence at Bambanda and Mpoto Hills would provide insight into differing elephant feeding behaviour there, and would help establish if human-elephant conflict has shifted to other areas along the VMWR boundary. In conjunction with boundary surveys and gathering reports from farmers, the diet study helps to inform the Department of National Parks and Wildlife (DNPW) management decisions regarding human-elephant conflict.

3.6. Literature cited

Anthony, B. P and Wasambo, J. (2009) Human-wildlife conflict study report: Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Malawi Department of National Parks and Wildlife. Technical Report

Chiyo, P. I., Cochrane, E. P., Naughton, L. and Basuta, G. I. (2005) Temporal patterns of crop raiding by elephants: a response to changes in forage quality or crop availability? *African Journal of Ecology*. Vol. 43(1), pp. 48-55

Graham, M. D., Douglas-Hamilton, I., Adams, W. M. Lee, P. C. (2009) The movement of African elephants in a human-dominated land-use mosaic. *Animal Conservation*. Vol. 12(5), pp.445-455.

Greene, W., Dierenfeld, E. S. and Mikota, S. (2019). A review of Asian and African elephant gastrointestinal anatomy, physiology and pharmacology. *Journal of Zoo and Aquarium Research*. Vol. 7(1)

Kerley, G. I. H., Landman, M., Kruger, L., Owen-Smith, N., Balvour, D., de Boer, W. F., Gaylard, A. Lindsay, K. and Slotow, R. (2008) Effects of Elephants on Ecosystems and Biodiversity. In: Mennell, K. G. and Scholes, R. J. (ed). *The 2007 scientific Assessment of Elephant Management in South Africa*. Pretoria: CSIR, pp. 101-147

Sievert, O., Sankhani, P. and Hintz, B. (unpublished) Using elephant pathways and dung to investigate human-wildlife conflict around Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve. NVT Final Grant Report 2022

Sievert, O., Evans, K., Mgoola, W. and Harwood, M, (2022) Early insights into the movements of Malawi's transboundary Elephants. *African Journal of Ecology*. Vol 00, pp. 1-5

4. Hippo count transects

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4.1. Introduction

The common hippopotamus (*Hippopotamus amphibius*, herein hippo) is currently listed as “Vulnerable” by the IUCN, with the main threat to their populations consisting of habitat degradation and hunting for bushmeat or ivory (Lewison and Pluháček 2017). The hippo population in VMWR is the only remaining population in Malawi’s Northern Region (Lewison and Pluháček 2017). Around Lake Kazuni, human-hippo conflict has been a common issue, with hippos often leaving the protected area to forage on crops (Anthony and Wasambo 2009), which has resulted in retaliatory killing. The killing of protected species in self-defence or defence of property remains legal within the scopes of the National Parks and Wildlife Act (2017). Neighbouring communities who were interviewed reported hippos as the second or third major “pest animal” around the VMWR area as they often fed on maize and cassava, while also causing damage to other crops through trampling and posed a direct threat to peoples’ lives (Anthony and Wasambo 2009).

Previous surveying of the VMWR hippo population reported a population estimate of 300 individuals (Lewison and Pluháček 2017). Lake Kazuni and the South Rukuru are the largest perennial water sources in VMWR. As such, hippos are reliant on these water bodies as their habitat during the dry season, thereby limiting the availability of suitable habitat. The continuous monitoring of hippo populations allows the Malawi Department of National Parks and Wildlife (DNPW) to react proactively to adverse population trends and evaluate the effect of anthropogenic pressure on the hippo population in VMWR.

4.2. Methods

Hippo counts were conducted via transects along the northern shore of Lake Kazuni, stretching from base camp to the mouth of the South Rukuru river (Figure 4.3a). During transects, all hippos were counted when the observers were positioned perpendicular to them to avoid double counting. For each hippo encountered, the observers waited a minimum of five minutes to allow potentially submerged individuals to resurface and thus be included in the count. Hippos were broadly categorised into adult (3+ years) and juvenile/infant age (<3 years) classes. The following parameters were also recorded: GPS location, date, time, number of individuals, their perpendicular (90°) distance from observer, the number of individuals in and outside the water and their distance from water (if applicable). GPS locations were calculated and adjusted for the centre of each observed pod (hippo grouping). Hippos were determined to be in a different pod if there was at least 50 metres between individuals.

Hippo transects were conducted eight times over the course of the expedition. However, the first transect was split into three parts on three consecutive days due to time constraints. Every subsequent transect was completed as a single event.

4.3. Results

A total of 698 hippos were counted around Lake Kazuni (Figure 4.3a) on transects during the expedition. Average pod size was 4.56 ± 4.92 SD (range: 1-26). The highest single transect count was 159 and obtained on the first transect, which was conducted over three days. The second highest count was 120 (transects 4 and 6), which were conducted on single days.

Figure 4.3a. Locations around Lake Kazuni where hippos were observed during the expedition period.

There was no significant difference in the total counted hippo numbers per transect between the 2022 hippo count and the ones conducted in 2018 and 2019 (Harwood et al. 2019, 2020) ($F(2, 31) = 1.9377, p = 0.1611$). A minor decrease of total counts per transect and maximum pod sizes was observed over the years (Figure 4.3b).

Figure 4.3b. Total number of hippos counted per transect and maximum pod sizes observed during 2018, 2019 and 2022 expeditions. 2018 consisted of three different groups, while 2019 and 2022 consisted of one and two respectively (i.e. repetition of transect numbers).

4.4. Discussion

During the 2022 expedition hippo counts it was found that there was a higher concentration of hippos towards the South Rukuru River. The habitat immediately adjacent to Lake Kazuni consists mostly of dense woodland, where graze availability is sparse. Hippos would therefore have to traverse longer distances to find suitable grazing grounds. The South Rukuru River on the other hand was surrounded by floodplains, which offered ample grazing and therefore supported a higher density of hippos.

Hippos use water bodies to cool down and to escape the sun during the day and emerge at night to forage (Lewison and Pluháček 2017). Lake Kazuni and the attached South Rukuru River are the only perennial water sources in VMWR, so the majority of the reserve’s hippo population should be located close to them. Thus, total counts of hippos on foot can also function as population estimates in relatively small areas where most of their diurnal range can be monitored. The data collected during the 2022 expedition counted lower total numbers than the 2018 and 2019 expeditions (Harwood et al. 2019, 2020), which had observed maximum single transect counts of 336 and 168 hippos respectively. While it is unlikely that either count was a complete total count of hippos in VMWR, it suggests that the population of hippos in VMWR has potentially declined substantially since 2018.

4.5. Outlook for future expedition work

A negative population trend was discernible from the data collected over all three expeditions (2018, 2019 and 2022). We will therefore continue to prioritise hippo population monitoring over the coming years, which will allow DNPW to intervene, should populations become unsustainably low.

4.6. Literature cited

Anthony, B. P and Wasambo, J. (2009). Human-wildlife conflict study report: Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Malawi Department of National Parks and Wildlife. Technical Report.

Harwood, A., Stone, E., Shevlin, K. and Hammer, M. (2019) From elephants to cats to butterflies: Monitoring biodiversity of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Expedition report 2018. Available via <https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Harwood, A., Stone, E., PetersonWood, B. and Hammer, M. (2020) From elephants to cats to butterflies: Monitoring biodiversity of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Expedition report 2019. Available via <https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Lewison, R. and Pluháček, J. (2017). Hippopotamus amphibius. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2017: e.T10103A18567364. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.20172.RLTS.T10103A18567364.en>. Accessed on 05 January 2023. National Parks and Wildlife Act (2017). Part IX, sections 73-75.

5. Camera trapping

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5.1. Introduction

Large mammal populations are declining globally (Ripple et al. 2015). Loss of large mammals can have cascading effects on ecosystems, including other mammal species, vegetation and habitats, as well as socio-economic consequences for humans (Diplock et al. 2018). Wildlife population declines also have considerable impacts on other animal populations (e.g., loss of prey species leads to a decline in carnivores), ecological effects such as a lack of proper seed dispersal, and a decrease in local tourism revenue (Diplock et al. 2018). In addition, little is known about how large mammal declines affect mutualistic species population trends (Galetti et al. 2018, Diplock et al. 2018).

Between 1970 and 2005, large mammal populations across Africa's protected areas have decreased by nearly 60% (Craigie et al. 2010). Poaching for ivory is a particularly grave threat, mainly to elephants (*Loxodonta africana*) (Maisels et al., 2013), leading to a 75% decline of elephant populations (Wittemyer et al. 2014). Similarly, large carnivore populations are facing threats from rising anthropogenic pressures (Nowell and Jackson 1996) and have faced extirpation across their historical range (Maisels et al. 2001). In Malawi, these species have already experienced devastating losses over many years (Munthali and Mkanda 2002).

Camera trapping has become one of the most popular tools for conservation researchers and wildlife managers to monitor wildlife. Camera traps are automated cameras triggered remotely by movement to capture records of animals. Today, remote cameras are used by researchers around the world, in a range of environments and for a variety of objectives. They have been established as a standard non-invasive surveying method, with the number of published papers utilising them continuing to increase (Rovero et al. 2013). The use of remote cameras for wildlife monitoring allows researchers to address questions that traditional survey techniques have been unable or difficult to address, particularly in detection of elusive and nocturnal species. The gathered data can provide valuable information on the occurrence of species and spatio-temporal ranging patterns, and consequently inform the implementation of long-term monitoring efforts for target species and adaptive management frameworks of the DNPW.

5.2. Methods

A total of 14 infrared camera traps (13 Bushnell, 1 Reconyx) were deployed along the southern road and parts of the northern road (Figure 5.2a), with approximately 2 km distance between stations. Camera traps were attached to trees roughly 80 cm above ground facing the road. On three occasions, additional camera traps were deployed for a duration of four days at baited sites (see Chapter 7). Images for all camera traps, including those used at baited sites, were included for analysis in this chapter. Camera traps were programmed with the same settings (16MP image size, 10s interval, medium sensitivity, medium night vision shutter speed), and took two images consecutively, allowing more reliable capture of multiple individuals in herds or groups of animals. Camera traps were set at the begin of the expedition and SD cards emptied and batteries swapped after nine days and recovered again after fourteen days. All pictures were analysed using Timelapse2 (v2.3.0.0). Only pictures containing animals were included in the analysis.

Figure 5.2a. Location of camera traps in VMWR during the 2022 expedition.

5.3. Results

Over the expedition period, a total of 40,804 images were taken during 190 trapping days (range 2-12 per camera trap). Of those images, 847 contained animals of 26 different species (Table 5.3a). Most other images (87%) were taken when camera traps were triggered by wind moving vegetation. As camera traps took two pictures consecutively, the total amount of images was inflated. Hence, all duplicate images that were taken within the two-image burst were discarded, resulting in 447 images of animals.

Table 5.3a. Species captured with camera traps and total occurrence in analysed pictures.
LC = least concern, NT = near threatened, VU = vulnerable, EN = endangered

Common Name	Scientific Name	IUCN Redlist status	Total captures of species
Ungulates			
African buffalo	<i>Syncerus caffer</i>	NT	13
African elephant	<i>Loxodonta africana</i>	EN	33
Bushbuck	<i>Tragelaphus scriptus</i>	LC	9
Bushpig	<i>Potamochoerus larvatus</i>	LC	7
Common duiker	<i>Sylvicapra grimmia</i>	LC	2
Greater kudu	<i>Tragelaphus strepsiceros</i>	LC	11
Hippopotamus	<i>Hippopotamus amphibius</i>	VU	139
Impala	<i>Aepyceros melampus</i>	LC	22
Sharpe's grysbok	<i>Raphicerus sharpei</i>	LC	1
Roan antelope	<i>Hippotragus equinus</i>	LC	3
Warthog	<i>Phacochoerus africanus</i>	LC	3
Carnivores			
African civet	<i>Civettictis civetta</i>	LC	23
African wild dog	<i>Lycaon pictus</i>	EN	4
Large-spotted genet	<i>Genetta maculata</i>	LC	11
Honey badger	<i>Mellivora capensis</i>	LC	18
Leopard	<i>Panthera pardus</i>	VU	1
Marsh mongoose	<i>Atilax paludinosus</i>	LC	1
Selous's mongoose	<i>Paracynictis selousi</i>	LC	1
Spotted hyaena	<i>Crocuta crocuta</i>	LC	13
White-tailed mongoose	<i>Ichneumia albicauda</i>	LC	1
Primates			
Vervet monkey	<i>Chlorocebus pygerythrus</i>	LC	4
Yellow baboon	<i>Papio cynocephalus</i>	LC	32
Other mammals			
African savanna hare	<i>Lepus victoriae</i>	LC	14
Cape porcupine	<i>Hystrix africaeaustralis</i>	LC	11
Birds			
Helmeted guineafowl	<i>Numida meleagris</i>	LC	67
Southern ground hornbill	<i>Bucorvus leadbeateri</i>	VU	3
Grand Total			447

Of the 26 species captured, two (African wild dog and African elephant) were listed as “endangered” on the IUCN Redlist of Threatened Species, three listed as “vulnerable” and one as “near threatened” (Figure 5.3b).

The only species of which there were more captures during the 2022 expedition compared to the previous two were of southern ground hornbill (3 captures in 2022, 1 in 2019, 1 in 2018), Selous's mongoose (1 capture in 2022, none in previous years) Sharpe's grysbok (captured only once in 2022) and African wild dog (4 captures in 2022, none in previous years) (Figures 5.3c and d).

Figure 5.3b. IUCN Redlist status of species captured on camera traps during the 2022 expedition. LC = least concern, NT = near threatened, VU = vulnerable, EN = endangered

Figure 5.3c. Number of camera trap captures for species across all three expeditions 2018, 2019, 2022 in VMWR.

Figure 5.3d. Number of camera trap captures for species across all three expeditions 2018, 2019, 2022 in VMWR. Vertical axis set to maximum of 70 to showcase species captured at low frequencies - if the vertical axis was set to the full 700, the bars for low frequency species would not be discernable (as in 5.3c).

Below are various images from the 2022 expedition camera trap effort that demonstrate the diversity of species captured.

Figure 5.3e. Roan antelope *Hippotragus equinus*.

Figure 5.3f. Honey badger *Mellivora capensis*

Figure 5.3g. Cape porcupine *Hystrix africaeaustralis*.

Figure 5.3h. Spotted hyaena *Crocuta crocuta*.

Figure 5.3i. African buffalo *Syncerus caffer*.

Figure 5.3j. Bushpig *Potamochoerus larvatus*.

Figure 5.3k. Spotted hyaena *Crocuta crocuta* with goat carcass from baited camera trap.

Figure 5.3l. White-tailed mongoose *Ichneumia albicauda*

Figure 5.3m. Leopard *Panthera pardus*.

Figure 5.3n. African civet *Civettictis civetta*.

Figure 5.3o. Large-spotted genet *Genetta maculata*.

Figure 5.3p. African elephant *Loxodonta africana*

Figure 5.3q. African wild dog *Lycaon pictus*.

5.4. Discussion

The 2018 and 2019 expeditions consisted of three and two groups of participants respectively (Harwood et al. 2019, 2020), whereas the 2022 expedition only had one group, probably because people were still cautious about signing up to an expedition as the Covid pandemic tailed off. Therefore, 2018 and 2019 had an increased survey effort, thus increasing the potential to capture various species, especially those that are in low densities in VMWR. Additionally, the risk of Human African Trypanosomiasis was deemed lower during the previous expeditions, allowing the groups to perform activities during the day and venture deeper into the reserve, where multiple camera traps were deployed over those years. Despite the constraints faced by the 2022 expedition, it yielded a higher number of species captured than the 2019 expedition, albeit with lower capture rates.

The capture rate of elephants in 2022 was substantially lower than during previous expeditions, despite common encounters with herds and individuals in the area surveyed by camera traps (see chapter 2). While much of the area close to the lake was surveyed for herd observations, only three camera traps were deployed adjacent to the lake, resulting in a relatively low probability to capture elephants along the northern side of the lake. Without targeting elephants specifically, the remaining camera traps were spaced out evenly on roads, to cover a larger area. Elephants rely on water availability during the dry season, concentrating their foraging around water bodies and thus reducing the probability of triggering camera traps further away from the lake.

The African wild dog was first captured in this expedition. The images have confirmed at least three individuals (distinguishable by their fur patterning) in the area, who are likely part of a dispersal group. Wild dog dispersals can occasionally consist of solitary individuals, more often comprising a few related individuals of a single sex in search of conspecifics of the opposite sex to form a new pack (Cozzi et al. 2020). Dispersal is a vital part of natural African wild dog population management, which enhances gene flow, decreases risk of local extirpation of smaller subpopulations and allows recolonisation of unoccupied ranges (Cozzi et al. 2020). Until recently, there were no known populations of African wild dogs in Malawi. The species was only recently, in 2021, reintroduced to two protected areas in Malawi's Southern Region. VMWR is part of the Malawi-Zambia Transfrontier Conservation Area, which neighbours the Luangwa Valley in Zambia. The Luangwa Valley hosts a sizeable population of African wild dogs. Communication between LWT and Zambian Carnivore Project staff established that none of the individuals captured on camera traps in VMWR were known in their database, however it is likely that they originated from the Luangwa Valley. The captured footage appears to be the first concrete evidence of African wild dogs in VMWR in over 20 years. Only approximately 6,400 individuals of the species remain in the wild and continuous anthropogenic pressure results in lower availability of suitable habitat (Woodroffe and Sillero-Zubiri 2020). Their resurfacing in VMWR therefore was a significant event. Future research will show whether this was a one-off event or whether the species will establish itself in VMWR. LWT will use the Biosphere Expeditions camera traps to continue to gather information on the species in VMWR over a more prolonged period. This has led to additional captures of this group of African wild dogs and has provided an updated total count of at least four individuals. The last sighting of them was on 29 October 2022.

5.5. Outlook for future expedition work

Camera trapping allows the remote and non-invasive monitoring of elusive species independent of time. As such, it offers a method to monitor and confirm presence of species that are frequently not observed in person. The continuous monitoring of the animal community composition in VMWR is an important task, and camera trapping will continue to play a vital role in that. Capturing footage of African wild dogs made evident how valuable the deployment of camera traps can be, as no direct observations have been attained of them to date. This is particularly important in an area with minimal tourism and where ranger patrols are spread out over a large area.

5.6. Literature cited

Cozzi, G., Behr, D. M., Webster, H. S., Claase, M., Bryce, C. M., Modise, B. and Ozgul, A. (2020) African Wild Dog Dispersal and Implications for Management. *The Journal of Wildlife Management*. Vol. 84(4), pp. 614-621.

Craigie, I.D., Baillie, J.E.M., Balmford, A., Carbone, C., Collen, B., Green, R.E. and Hutton, J.M. (2010) Large mammal population declines in Africa's protected areas. *Biological Conservation*. 143:2221-2228

Diplock, N., Johnston, K., Mellon, A., Mitchell, L., Moore, M., Schneider, D., Taylor, A., Whitney, J., Zegar, K., Kioko, J. and Kiffner, C. (2018) Large mammal declines and the incipient loss of mammal-bird mutualisms in an African savanna ecosystem. *PLoS ONE* 13(8): e0202536.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0202536>

Galetti, M., Moleón, M., Jordano, P., Pires, M.M., Guimarães, P.R., Pape, T., Nichols, E., Hansen, D., Olesen, J.M., Munk, M., and de Mattos, J.S. (2018) Ecological and evolutionary legacy of megafauna extinctions. *Biological Reviews*. 93(2):845–862.

Harwood, A., Stone, E., Shevlin, K. and Hammer, M. (2019) From elephants to cats to butterflies: Monitoring biodiversity of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Expedition report 2018. Available via <https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Harwood, A., Stone, E., PetersonWood, B. and Hammer, M. (2020) From elephants to cats to butterflies: Monitoring biodiversity of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Expedition report 2019. Available via <https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Maisels, F., Strindberg, S., Blake, S., Wittemyer, G., Hart, J., Williamson, E.A., Aba'a, R., Abitsi, G., Ambahe, R.D., Amsini, F., Bakabana, P.C., Hicks, T.C., Bayogo, R.E., Bechem, M., Beyers, R.L., Bezangoye, A.N., Boundja, P., Bout, N., Akou, M.E., Bene, L.B., Fosso, B., Greengrass, E., Grossmann, F., Ikamba-Nkulu, C., Ilambu, O., Inogwabini, B.I., Iyenguet, F., Kiminou, F., Kokangoye, M., Kujirakwinja, D., Latour, S., Liengola, I., Mackaya, Q., Madidi, J., Madzoke, B., Makoumbou, C., Malanda, G.A., Malonga, R., Mbani, O., Mbendzo, V.A., Ambassa, E., Ekinde, A., Mihindou, Y., Morgan, B.J., Motsaba, P., Moukala, G., Mounquengui, A., Mowawa, B.S., Ndzai, C., Nixon, S., Nkumu, P., Nzolani, F., Pinteá, L., Plumptre, A., Rainey, H., de Semboli, B.B., Serckx, A., Stokes, E., Turkali, A., Vanleeuwe, H., Vosper, A., and Warren, Y. (2013) Devastating decline of forest elephants in central Africa. *PLOS One* 8, e59469.

Maisels, F., Keming, E., Kemei, M. and Toh, C. (2001) The extirpation of large mammals and implications for mountain forest conservation: the case of the Kilum-Ijum Forest. Northwest Province, Cameroon. *Oryx*. 35: 322- 331

Munthali, S.M. & Mkanda, F. X (2002) The plight of Malawi's wildlife: is translocation of animals the solution? *Biodiversity and Conservation*. 11:751-768

Nowell, K. and Jackson, P. (1996) Wild Cats. Status Survey and Conservation Action Plan. IUCN/SSC Cat Specialist Group. IUCN, Gland, 382 p.

Ripple, J.W., Newsome, T.M., Wolf, C., Dirzo, R., Everatt, K.T., Galetti, M., Hayward, M.W., Kerley, G.I.H., Levi, T., Lindsey, P.A., Macdonald, D.W., Malhi, Y., Painter, L.E., Sandom, C.J., Terborgh, J., and van Valkenburgh, B. (2015) Collapse of the world's largest herbivores. *Science Advances*. 1(4):e1400103

Rovero, F., Zimmermann, F., Merzi, D., and Meek, P. (2013) "Which camera trap type and how many do I need?" A review of camera features and study designs for a range of wildlife research applications. *Hystrix*. doi:10.4404/hystrix-24.2-6316

Wittemyer, G., Northrup, J.M., Blanc, J., Douglas-Hamilton, I., Omondo, P., and Burnham, K.P. (2014) Illegal killing for ivory drives global decline in African elephants. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 111(36): 13117-13121

Woodroffe, R. & Sillero-Zubiri, C. 2020. *Lycaon pictus* (amended version of 2012 assessment). The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2020: e.T12436A166502262. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2020-1.RLTS.T12436A166502262.en>

6. Invertebrate sampling

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6.1 Introduction

Since 2019, the LWT has received 101 pangolins confiscated from the illegal wildlife trade that required rehabilitation. Of these, 66 have been released back into the wild across Malawi's various protected areas. To consider VMWR as a potential release site for pangolins that were confiscated from the illegal wildlife trade, all habitat requirements must be met. These include access to water, sufficient shelter opportunities such as burrows or natural crevices and ample food availability. Pangolin diet consists solely of ants and termites. As such, the presence and adequate abundance of palatable species is an important factor in determining release site suitability. During previous research efforts, the LWT identified preferred species for several pangolins of different sexes and ages, however the occurrence of these species in VMWR remained unconfirmed.

Sampling through pitfall traps can provide a solid preliminary understanding of the presence and relative abundance of different ground-dwelling invertebrate species (Woodcock 2005). Pitfall trapping is a useful method in various habitat types and independent of time of day. It is therefore the best way for us to better understand the presence and distribution of ant species within VMWR, which will help inform our pangolin rehabilitation and release efforts.

6.2. Methods

A grid of 4 x 6 sampling containers (63 mm x 47 mm Ø) was set up in two representative habitats (floodplains and woodland). Containers were labelled according to their position within the grid. Each container was dug into the soil until its rim was level with the ground. Containers were spaced 5 m apart. Each container was filled with a solution consisting of aroma-neutral soap and water as a killing agent, with the rims of the containers rubbed with a thin film of honey as bait.

For the initial set-up, only every second container was opened (lid removed) and filled. This helped account for potential digging-in effect (Jiménez-Carmona et al. 2019). Containers were topped up with solution every 24-hrs to counteract evaporation throughout the day. After the first 24 hrs, containers were sampled and re-set along with the closed containers, thus allowing for the full grid to be set up. Containers were then sampled every 48 hrs. Sampling was done by slowly pouring the contents of the containers into labelled plastic tubes. A small plastic tray was held underneath the tube to capture any spilled specimen, which were then transferred to the tube using thin tweezers. After each sampling occasion, all containers within the grid were cleaned with water, refilled with solution and the honey bait was replaced.

Samples were processed immediately upon return to base camp. Processing of samples consisted of emptying the contents of each tube into a petri dish. Citizen scientists then selected representative specimens within the sample. Photographs were then taken of the flank, dorsal and ventral view for each specimen using a microscope with an attached digital camera, using the software AmScope (v4.11.20131.20220108) (Figure 6.2a). For larger species, a close-up view of the head including mandibles was also taken. All pictures were saved in appropriately named folders and used for later identification of the species.

The specimens were then transferred into a clean tube with 95% ethanol as a preservative in case later reference was required. While the main target of the exercise was ants, pictures of any other invertebrates caught in pitfall traps were also taken and saved in a separate folder and then uploaded to iNaturalist (see chapter 8). For any samples that could not be processed the same day, the soap solution was swapped with 95% ethanol as a preservative and processing took place the following day.

Figure 6.2a. Citizen scientists analysing invertebrate samples under the microscope at the VMWR camp. Picture courtesy of Gitta Voss.

Figure 6.2b-e. Examples of ant species captured during pit-fall trapping:
(b) soldier and (c) worker castes of *Camponotus* sp., (d) *Crematogaster* sp., (e) *Polyrhachis gagatas*.

6.3. Results

A two-tailed student's t-test showed no significant difference between species composition and their capture rates from samples collected on the first and second day (i.e. treatment to account for digging-in effect) ($t(7) = -2.04$, $p = 0.081$).

Seven different species were identified from the collected samples, of which only *Aenictus* sp. and *Aphaenogaster swammerdami* were captured more frequently in woodland habitat (Figure 6.3a). There was no significant difference between the total number of captures between the two habitat types ($t(10) = 0.439$, $p = 0.670$).

Figure 6.3a. Relative capture rate of ant species in floodplain and woodland habitat.

During the invertebrate analysis, 451 pictures of other invertebrate species were taken, including the taxonomic orders Araneae, Diptera, Orthoptera, Lepidoptera, Hymenoptera, Hemiptera, Coleoptera, Blattodea and Isoptera.

6.4. Discussion

The methodology applied accounted for species occurrence and capture rate, but not for their abundance. Some ant species travel above ground in large colonies, while others split into smaller foraging parties, so any analysis of abundance from these pitfall traps would be strongly linked to species behaviour and thus introduce bias (Carroll and Janzen 1973, Wong and Guénard 2017). Furthermore, pitfall trapping is mostly applicable for ground-dwelling species, but less efficient for species that have a predominantly arboreal or subterranean lifestyle (Wong and Guénard 2017). Finally, ant species cover a large dietary range and baiting with honey may have skewed the results in favour of ant species attracted by sweet bait (Carroll and Janzen 1973, Greenslade 1972).

LWT is conducting research aiming to establish the preferred food items of pangolins in protected areas across Malawi. Preliminary results from Malawi's Central Region identified frequently occurring ant species including *Anoplolepis custodiens* and *A. swammerdami*. For rehabilitation purposes, this indicates that there is an overlap in species compositions between Malawi's Central and Northern Regions (where VMWR is located), thus suggesting that pangolins who have originated from the Central Region of Malawi may be able to adapt easily to VMWR as there are readily available familiar food resources.

6.5. Outlook for future expedition work

The research gathered representative data of ant species composition in two of VMWR's most representative habitat types at the end of the dry season. Limitations to travelling further into the reserve due to Human African Trypanosomiasis resulted in the habitats being chosen close to Lake Kazuni where tsetse fly densities were low. For a more holistic understanding of the species occurrence in VMWR, surveying of the central and northern parts of the reserve would be helpful, particularly the addition of marsh habitat in the north-western part of VMWR as it might host a different species composition. A comparison between species assemblages during the dry and wet seasons would also give a more thorough understanding of food availability for pangolins.

6.6. Literature cited

Carroll, C. R. and Janzen, D. H. (1973) Ecology of foraging by ants. Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics. Vol. 4, pp. 231-257

Greenslade, P. J. M. (1972) Comparative ecology of four tropical ant species. Insectes Sociaux. Vol. 19(3), pp. 195–212

Jiménez-Carmona, F., Carpintero, S. and Reyes-López, J. L. (2019). The digging-in effect on ant studies with pitfall traps: influence of type of habitat and sampling time. Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata. Vol. 167(10), pp.906-914.

Woodcock, B. A. Chapter 3 - Pitfall Trapping in Ecological Studies. In: Leather, S. Insect Sampling in Forest Ecosystems (2005) Wiley-Blackwell. Pp. 37-57

Wong, M. K. L. and Guénard, B. (2017). Subterranean ants: summary and perspectives on field sampling methods, with notes on diversity and ecology (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). Myrmecological News. Vol 25, pp. 1-16.

7. Hyaena call-ins

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7.1. Introduction

Spotted hyaenas (*Crocuta crocuta*) are the most abundant and widespread large carnivore species in Africa and play a vital role in carnivore compositions of natural ecosystems, despite this, their conservation status is often overlooked (Bohm and Höhner 2015, Davis et al. 2022). Carnivore composition within protected areas is largely affected by interspecies competition, highlighting the need to assess accurately carnivore populations for effective management (Davis et al. 2022). Additionally, spotted hyaena population size is a good indicator for ecosystem health, as the species is affected by factors including prey density, presence of other carnivores, as well as human encroachment and conflict (Cozzi et al. 2013, Davis et al. 2022).

Surveying hyaenas in VMWR through conventional methods such as transects or total counts would be impractical due to dense vegetation, reduced road network and cryptic hyaena nature due to low levels of tourism (i.e. the animals are not habituated to humans and their vehicles). We therefore used camera trapping as a non-intrusive way of surveying the population, but this activity was mainly limited to the road network in VMWR (see chapter 5). Call-ins, on the other hand, have been used as a successful survey method for lions and spotted hyaena in other parts of Africa (Cozzi et al. 2013, Mwampeta et al. 2021), particularly when using bait as an incentive to approach the call-in station. We therefore sought to test this survey method in VMWR for the first time, during the 2022 expedition, in order to assess its viability for hyaena population monitoring in this region.

7.2. Methods

Call-ins using a [FOXPRO](#) Inferno call-in kit were conducted after sunset on three separate occasions. A location with open habitat for improved visibility was selected along the southern road, with each subsequent call-in event being located at least 3 km further along the road. The location was baited with a fresh goat carcass, which was staked into the ground approximately 5 m from a camera trap. Prior to the commencement of calling-in, 20 min were spent in absolute silence, to help settle the area after the disturbance of setting up the call-in site. Call-ins were conducted using a selection of pig and buffalo calf in distress and hyaena vocalisations. Audio files were played for 5 min alternated by 5 min of silence for a total of 1.5 hrs. After each audio playback, the speakers were turned by 90°. Throughout this time, spotlights were used at regular intervals to scan for approaching animals. At the beginning of each surveying period, GPS location of the set-up, weather conditions and the start time of the call-ins were recorded. For any observed animal, the time, number of animals and number of different age classes (if discernible) were recorded, along with information on their behaviour, an estimate of distance to the observer, and a compass bearing.

7.3. Results

No hyaenas responded to the call-ins, neither were any individuals observed vocalising in response to the audio playbacks.

7.4. Discussion

This activity yielded no results. Part of the issue may be linked to the speaker's volume, which did not appear to be loud enough to carry over a large distance. Coupled with windy conditions, it was likely that the call-ins only covered a small area around the research vehicle. Furthermore, the lake created a natural boundary towards the south, from where hyaenas could not approach, thus limiting the effective survey area.

Camera traps deployed to monitor the carcasses after the monitoring group's departure did not pick up any hyaenas. Four pictures were captured of African wild dogs passing one goat carcass, potentially being attracted by its smell from afar. However, they did not appear to stop at the carcass or make use of it. After checking the first camera trap deployed after a call-in event, the set bait was missing and stakes had been removed. The camera trap at that site had malfunctioned and did not capture any footage at night, so we were unable to determine what animal made use of this carcass. However, on inspection of the other camera traps, a spotted hyaena was captured carrying a carcass, colour pattern of which matched the goat used as bait. Other camera traps showed that hyaenas generally utilised the southern area of the reserve (see chapter 5), in which all call-in stations were located. However, given the close proximity of communities near the southern boundary of VMWR, it is possible that these individuals have experienced heightened persecution prior to the erection of the fence in 2021. Heightened persecution would have resulted in hyaenas in this area being more careful and skittish and also decreased the likelihood of them investigating a bait site or call-in. Regardless, the purpose of this work was to test the success of call-ins as a survey method in VMWR. Our results indicate that camera trapping along road networks is a more successful method.

7.5. Outlook for future expedition work

While the hyaena call-ins as tried in 2022 were unsuccessful, it might be possible to adjust the methodology, ideally with stronger speakers, so it can be tried again during future expeditions. Locations should be spread further apart to access different ranges and potentially subpopulations of hyaenas. Pre-baiting an area for two days prior to conducting the call-up may also assist in ensuring hyaenas are within the area when the call-up occurs.

7.6. Literature cited

- Bohm, T. and Höner, O. R. (2015) *Crocuta crocuta*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2015: e.T5674A45194782. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2015-2.RLTS.T5674A45194782.en>
- Cozzi, G., Broekhuis, F., McNutt, J. W. and Schmid, B. (2013) Density and habitat use of lions and spotted hyaenas in northern Botswana and the influence of survey and ecological variables on call-in survey estimation. *Biodiversity Conservation*. Vol. 22, pp. 2937-2956
- Davis, R. S., Gentle, L. K., Stone, E. K., Uzal, A. and Yarnell, R. W. (2022) A review of spotted hyaena population estimates highlights the need for greater utilisation of spatial capture-recapture methods. *Journal of Vertebrate Biology*. Vol. 71(22017), pp. 1-15.
- Mwampeta, S. B., Wilton, C. M., Mkasanga, I. J., Masindle, L. M., Ranke, P. S., Røskraft, E., Fyumagwa, R. and Belant, J. L. (2021) Lion and spotted hyaena distributions within a buffer area of the Serengeti-Mara ecosystem. *Scientific Reports*. Vol. 11(22289).

8. iNaturalist

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8.1. Introduction

[iNaturalist](#) was founded in 2008 and partnered with the California Academy of Science in 2014 and National Geographic in 2017 to reach its current state as a “community for naturalists”, as stated on the iNaturalist website, and “an online social network of people sharing biodiversity information to help each other learn about nature” (Loarie 2022). The platform compiles data provided by citizen scientists around the globe, in the form of evidence-based observations across all taxa that require to be confirmed by other users to achieve research grade. The form of evidence required ranges from pictures of the organisms, their vocalisations to indirect signs such as tracks, faeces, feathers or quills.

The LWT started using iNaturalist in 2022 to create species catalogues across all their field sites, including VMWR. The species catalogues and compiled information about them help any prospective expedition participants, researchers or volunteers to connect better to their environment and acquire knowledge about the site they are working in.

8.2. Methods

All expedition participants were instructed how to utilise the iNaturalist app or website to upload observations. Evidence of organisms was collected *ad lib* around base camp or during field activities. All uploads made during the expedition period were automatically added to the project “Biosphere Malawi Expedition 2022 – African Wildlife & Elephants” after existing accounts of participants or newly created ones for the expedition were added to the project.

Additionally, camera trap footage and pictures taken of invertebrates under the microscope during invertebrate sampling were also added to the project.

8.3. Results

Over the course of the expedition, 397 observations of 138 species were logged. Of those, 174 (75%) achieved research grade status. The uploaded observations covered six different taxa, of which birds made up 62% (n = 74) of all observed species (Figure 8.3a). Seven camera trap pictures were uploaded to supplement the species account of mammals (African wild dog, bushpig, honey badger, leopard, Sharpe’s grysbok, spotted hyena and white-tailed mongoose). Once microscope photographs from invertebrate sampling were uploaded, they made up the majority of observations (40%, n = 159), of which only three were identified to species level.

Figure 8.3a. Breakdown of taxa uploaded to iNaturalist during the expedition.

8.4. Discussion

The statistics feature of iNaturalist requires identification to species level, or at higher classification, and several confirmations by identifiers. Few users specialise in invertebrates, which resulted in a low rate of identification to species level for ants. Therefore, the total species count shown on the bio-blitz page remains relatively low compared to the number of observations made. That being said, it is important to upload these observations as specialists can make identifications at any time. Invertebrate biodiversity has experienced substantial declines over the last decades (Sánchez-Bayo and Wyckhuys, 2020). However, invertebrates commonly remain overlooked in conservation despite the vital ecosystem services they provide, such as pollination, decomposition and nutrient cycling (Eisenhauer and Hines 2021). Eisenhauer et al. (2019) recommended a global approach to the compilation of past and present data on invertebrates to investigate spatio-temporal trends and re-surveying of sites. The expedition’s work of sampling invertebrates and making records publicly available on iNaturalist allows scientists to follow these spatio-temporal trends for invertebrates in VMWR.

Collecting adequate evidence of species presence can be difficult, particularly for elusive and cryptic species, due to low encounter probabilities. The supplementation through data collected from other activities (invertebrate sampling and camera trapping) accounted for 42% of all observations made, which demonstrates the importance of these methods in biodiversity logging.

8.5. Outlook for future expedition work

iNaturalist offers automated tools for summative statistics for species observed. This allows for a simple comparison of total species observed at different taxonomic levels between subsequent Biosphere Expeditions projects. As a long-term project, iNaturalist cataloguing helps to create updated species accounts for the area of operation that is accessible to scientists across the globe. The data collected through encountered species, and in addition the encounter rates over several years during future expeditions, can provide valuable insights into changes in species composition and abundance over time. Finally, iNaturalist also allows future expedition participants to get a grasp of what species could potentially be observed in VMWR and provides a comprehensive platform to learn about the species prior to coming on expedition. This data collection and logging activity will therefore be continued.

8.6. Literature cited

Eisenhauer, N., Bonn, A. and Guerra, C. A. (2019) Recognizing the quiet extinction of invertebrates. *Nature Communications*. Vol. 10(50)

Eisenhauer, N. and Hines, J. (2021) Invertebrate biodiversity and conservation. *Current Biology*. Vol.31(19), pp. 1214-1218.

Loarie, S. (2022). iNaturalist – What is it? Available at: <https://www.inaturalist.org/pages/what+is+it>. Last accessed on 06 January 2023.

Sánchez-Bayo, F. and Wyckhuys, K. A. G (2020). Further evidence for a global decline of entomofauna. *Austral Entomology*. Vol. 60(1), pp. 9-26.